

Publication of ISA 2026 Contributions in the Peer Community Journal (PCJ) through PCI Archaeology

Presenters at the 45th International Symposium on Archaeometry (ISA 2026) are invited to submit a full manuscript for publication through **Peer Community in Archaeology** and, upon recommendation, in the **Peer Community Journal** (<https://isa2026torino.it/publication-of-isa-2026/>).

ISA 2026 does not publish a traditional proceedings volume. Instead, submitted manuscripts undergo a rigorous, transparent, and community-driven peer-review process coordinated by PCI Archaeology. Manuscripts that receive a positive recommendation are subsequently published as peer-reviewed Diamond Open Access articles in the Peer Community Journal within a thematic collection associated with ISA 2026.

Who Can Submit?

Submission is open to all authors presenting a contribution at ISA 2026, including both oral and poster presentations.

Authors may submit **one manuscript** for each contribution accepted for presentation at the conference.

The submitted manuscript must be **clearly related to the research presented at ISA 2026**, although it does not need to reproduce the presentation exactly. Authors may expand, refine, or further develop specific aspects of their work.

From Submission to Publication: A Step-by-Step Guide

The papers will go through the process outlined here and graphically depicted in the following diagram:

Step 1 – Prepare Your Manuscript

Authors should prepare a complete manuscript following the guidelines and formatting requirements provided by PCI Archaeology:

https://archaeo.peercommunityin.org/help/guide_for_authors

The manuscript should present original research and include all relevant data, methods, results, and references.

Step 2 – Deposit the Preprint

Authors must obtain a DOI by **depositing their manuscript in the ISA 2026 community on Zenodo** <https://zenodo.org/communities/isa2026>.

IMPORTANT: A Zenodo account is required to deposit a manuscript. If you do not already have one, please create it before starting the submission process.

Whenever possible, associated datasets, code, images, analytical workflows, and supplementary materials should also be deposited in the open repository, unless ethical, legal, cultural heritage, or confidentiality considerations prevent open sharing.

Step 3 – Submit to PCI Archaeology

Submit the DOI of your preprint through the PCI Archaeology platform and **indicate in the cover letter** that the manuscript is being submitted as part of the ISA 2026 thematic collection.

IMPORTANT: In the cover letter, authors should **indicate the ISA 2026 thematic session** associated with their contribution. This will ensure that the submitted manuscript is assigned to the PCI Archaeology recommenders (guest editors) managing the corresponding thematic session.

Step 4 – Get Recommended

The manuscript will undergo open peer review coordinated by PCI Archaeology recommenders. Reviews, editorial decisions, and recommendations are publicly available, ensuring transparency and accountability throughout the evaluation process.

Authors may be invited to revise their manuscript before a final recommendation is issued.

Step 5 – Publication

Once recommended by PCI Archaeology, the manuscript will be published in the Peer Community Journal as a peer-reviewed Diamond Open Access article within the ISA 2026 collection.

Publication is **free of charge** for authors and readers.

SUBMISSION DEADLINE: 30 October 2026